

The tracking and measurement of the beam-related parameters at Belle II

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ABSTRACT

The tracking system of Belle II consists of a silicon vertex detector (VXD) and a cylindrical drift chamber (CDC), both operating in a magnetic field created by the main solenoid of 1.5 T and final focusing magnets. The experiment is taking data since 2019 with high-quality and stable tracking performance. We present the tracking-based calibration of the beam characteristics and their interaction region, which are critical for the many high-precision measurements in the physics program. We also discuss possible improvements in the silicon strip vertex detector track finding, exploiting Hough transformation instead of the current approach which is based on the trained MC patterns.

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1 Introduction

The Belle II experiment [1] belongs to the next generation of the B -factories and its main mission is to study the CP -violation in the $B\bar{B}$ system and rare decays of B mesons. Despite the name, Belle II also probes charmed particles, τ leptons, performs dark sector searches and serves in addition a broad physics program. The experiment is located at the SuperKEKB collider [2], which accelerates electrons to 7 GeV and positrons to 4 GeV, so that the centre-of-mass (CM) energy of the collisions is 10.58 GeV, corresponding to the $\Upsilon(4S)$ resonance mass. The $\Upsilon(4S)$ resonance decays almost exclusively to $B\bar{B}$. As the $\Upsilon(4S)$ mass is just slightly above the production threshold, the B mesons are nearly at rest in the CM frame. Asymmetric beam energies lead to a boost of the $B\bar{B}$ system, so that the lifetimes of the B mesons can be measured via the displaced vertices.

Up to now SuperKEKB has achieved a peak luminosity of $5 \times 10^{34} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ which is more than twice the record luminosity set by Belle [3], but still about 20 times smaller than the design luminosity.

High luminosity is achieved by a significant reduction of the vertical beam size ("nano beam" scheme) and by increasing the beam currents. Over the full lifespan SuperKEKB is expected to deliver an integrated luminosity of 50 ab^{-1} . So far before the Long Shutdown 1, which started in Summer 2022, the luminosity of 430 fb^{-1} have been recorded, which roughly corresponds to the total integrated luminosity recorded by BaBar. The data taking will continue in Fall 2023 after the upgrade.

The design of the Belle II experiment is motivated by the high instantaneous luminosity and the challenges that come with it. In addition it respects the asymmetry in energies of the colliding particles, i.e. the detector has better coverage in the forward region than in backward.

The tracking system (Fig. 1) is made up of three tracking detectors: the pixel detector (PXD) and the strip vertex detector (SVD), which are commonly summarized as the vertex detector (VXD), as well as the central drift chamber (CDC). The PXD is installed right outside the beam pipe and consists of two layers,

Figure 1: The Belle II vertex detector (VXD) (a) and the Central Drift Chamber (CDC) (b).

based on the DEPFET Pixel Technology [4]. Currently, the first layer of 16 modules is fully installed but only four modules from 24 modules of the second layer are mounted. One of the advantages of the DEPFET is a very low material budget of about 0.2% of a radiation length. The PXD allows for a very precise measurement of the impact parameter of tracks as the inner layer is installed at a radius of just about 1.4 cm and the pixel size is $50 \mu\text{m}$ in the azimuthal direction. The SVD encloses the PXD and consists of four layers of double-sided silicon strip detectors, which corresponds to a thickness of about 0.7% radiation lengths. It has an excellent hit time resolution of about 3 ns. This allows the SVD to provide robust tracking despite the background levels, also for standalone tracking. The outermost tracking detector is the CDC, which consists of 56 layers of wires grouped in alternating superlayers of axial and stereo wires. Stereo wires are skewed by an angle between 45.4 and 74 mrad in the positive and negative direction with respect to the axis of the beam and are necessary to determine the longitudinal position of tracks. Most importantly, the CDC provides a very high momentum resolution as it covers the major part of the tracking volume up to $l \times r = 2.3 \text{ m} \times 2.2 \text{ m}$.

2 Track finding

2.1 Overview

A detailed overview about the track finding at Belle II can be found in [5], the track-finding sequence is summarized in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: The Belle II tracking workflow (a), where VXDTE2 algorithm is planned to be replaced by SVDHough, and the example of the fitted tracks in the transverse plane shown together with the hits (b). The wires in CDC are visible as dots and SVD modules as line segments.

The CDC track finding consists of two independent algorithms and it is used as the baseline. In the second step, SVD hits are added to the previously found tracks making use of a Combinatorial Kalman Filter (CKF). The third step considers the unused SVD hits and tries to reconstruct tracks out of them. These SVD standalone tracks are then extrapolated to the CDC again via another CKF. Finally all independently found tracks are merged to a single collection that is then extrapolated to the PXD in the final step by a third CKF.

To find the tracks in CDC, first the global approach based on the Legendre parameters is used, consequently the remaining hits are found using Cellular Automaton which works better for tracks from the secondary decays.

2.2 SVD tracking based on Hough transformation

As mentioned in the previous section, in addition to the SVD tracks obtained by an extrapolation from CDC via CKF, the SVD standalone tracks are also considered (Fig. 2). This is especially useful for the low- p_T tracks which have high curvature and do not reach the CDC.

The algorithm, known as VXDTE2, which is still used by default, is based on filtering the track candidates using the relation maps between SVD sectors calculated by MC and on applying Cellular Automaton to find the tracks [5].

The newly developed algorithm SVDHough finds tracks in the Hough space instead [6]. First, the x, y coordinates* of the hits in SVD are transformed via a conformal transformation to x', y'

$$x', y' = \frac{x, y}{x^2 + y^2}, \quad (1)$$

so that circles are transformed into lines, see Fig. 3 (a). This transformation preserves track angle at the

*At Belle II the z-axis of the laboratory frame is defined as the central axis of the solenoid, with its positive direction defined by the direction of the electron beam. The distance between this axis and the actual interaction point changes in time and it has been always smaller than 0.1 cm.

Figure 3: SVD hits before and after the conformal transformation (a) and curves obtained from hits via Hough transformation (b) [6].

origin of coordinate system. Notice, that for the transformed track, the curvature is encoded into the distance of the line from the origin. In the next step, the Hough transformation (HT)

$$\rho = x' \cos \theta + y' \sin \theta \quad (2)$$

is applied on the hit coordinates (x', y') , Fig. 3 (b). It converts each hit to the sinusoidal curve. It would be computationally intense to calculate all the intersections analytically as there can be hundreds of hits in SVD. Therefore, the "binary" search approach visualised in Fig. 3 (b) is used to find the region with the highest density of curves. In this way, the $\mathcal{O}(n^2)$ problem is converted to $\mathcal{O}(n \log n)$. The division is stopped if less than three lines from different SVD layers pass it or if a maximal number of divisions is reached. This approach allows to find the local maxima, corresponding to the track candidates.

In Fig. 4 the performance of the both variants of the SVD standalone tracking is compared using simulated events. We define the MC tracks which are created using the true simulated hits. On the other hand, there are Pattern Recognition (PR) tracks found by the tracking algorithm. MC track and PR track are *matched* if the PR track contains at least 5% hits of the MC track and at the same time more than 66.6% hits of the PR track are from the MC track [6]. The MC track is *found* if it is *matched* at least to one PR track. The track finding efficiency plotted on the right is a fraction of *found* MC tracks w.r.t. all MC tracks in the event. Notice, that such definition considers only traces from MC particles that are in the fiducial volume of the Belle II and the finding efficiency of 100% is in principle feasible. It can be seen that the SVDhough performs better in the forward and backward region than the older algorithm. There can be multiple PR tracks *matched* to the MC track. That can happen for the low p_T curling tracks, which travel through the tracking volume multiple times, or if the track from the particle is found in multiple sub-detectors but these are not merged together. Even in this case, there is always a single PR track which has the best matching quality and the remaining PR tracks are tagged as clones. Fraction of clone PR tracks w.r.t. all PR tracks in the event is shown in left part of Fig. 4. It can be seen, that for the low p_T high-curvature tracks with $p_T \approx 0.05$ GeV, which are mostly in the SVD volume, there is a substantial reduction of the clones with the new algorithm.

3 Beam-related Parameters

3.1 Motivation

An important advantage of the B factories colliding electrons with positrons compared to the experiments based on hadron collisions (e.g. LHCb) is the clean even topology. At LHC there are hundreds of particles produced per bunch-crossing, both from the primary interaction as well as from the Pile-Up. Consequently, there is huge combinatorial background, especially for decays into neutral particles [7]. On the other hand, at Belle II in typical interaction ~ 10 final-state particles are produced which are the decay products of B

and \bar{B} in case of the $e^+e^- \rightarrow \Upsilon(4S) \rightarrow B\bar{B}$ processes. As no other particles than the pair of B mesons are produced, the kinematic properties of the B mesons can be constrained from the energy-momentum conservation using the momenta of the beams[†]. In addition, the knowledge of the production region of the $B\bar{B}$ pair, so-called beam spot, allows to improve the precision of the vertex positions as well as particle momenta. Belle II achieves high instantaneous luminosity by the nano-beam scheme, where the luminous region in the vertical direction has only ~ 100 nm and is planned to have 50 nm, when the instantaneous luminosity will be increased. Therefore, the y production coordinate is much more constrained than at Belle or BaBar where the vertical beam spot size was $\sim 5 \mu\text{m}$ [8].

Excellent Belle II tracking performance together with the tighter beam spot constraint allowed to measure lifetimes of the charmed hadrons like D^+ and D^0 [9] and Λ_c^+ [10] with the world leading precision although the luminosity of the analysed data was smaller compared to Belle or BaBar.

The knowledge of the momenta of the colliding particles is utilized to better reconstruct the invariant mass of the B meson. The beam-constrained invariant mass is defined as

$$M_{bc} = \sqrt{(E_{\text{beam}}^*)^2 - (p_B^*)^2}, \quad (3)$$

where $E_{\text{beam}}^* = \sqrt{s}/2$ and p_B^* is the beam energy and B meson momentum in the CM frame. Using this quantity one can achieve much better mass resolution and, consequently, better signal to background discrimination than with the classical invariant mass. Furthermore, the beam momenta are also used to perform the transformation to the CM system or, for example, to get the $\Upsilon(4S)$ velocity which is essential in the time-dependent CP violation measurements.

In addition, by measuring the beam momenta at Belle II we can monitor the performance of the accelerator, for example that it really operates with CM energy exactly equal to the $\Upsilon(4S)$ resonance mass.

Both the beam spot parameters and beam momenta in general differ to the nominal values and vary with time, therefore, they have to be continuously measured. At Belle II, we have two kinds of the simulation, run-independent and run-dependent, where in the second one the time dependence of the beam-related quantities is taken into account.

[†]By "beam momentum" we always understand momentum of a single particle in the beam.

Figure 4: Clone rate of tracks (a) as a function of track transverse momentum and the tracking efficiency (b) as a function of the dip angle λ of the matched MC particle. On top of that, the track density distribution with an arbitrary normalization is overlaid. The results using default tracking workflow (Fig. 2) are represented by orange lines. The blue lines indicate an alternative scenario where VXDTF2 is replaced by SVDHough algorithm [6].

3.2 Beam spot

By beam spot (also known as luminous region) we understand the spatial probability density of the primary interactions. This probability density can be approximated by 3D Gaussian function

$$p(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{\det^{\frac{1}{2}}(2\pi\mathbf{V})} \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_{\text{IP}})^T \mathbf{V}^{-1}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_{\text{IP}})\right), \quad (4)$$

which is characterised by 9 parameters. It is the position of the beam spot center \mathbf{x}_{IP} (3 parameters) and the covariance matrix \mathbf{V} which is 3×3 symmetric matrix (6 parameters) describing beam spot sizes and orientation. Notice that the surface of equal probability density is an ellipsoid, \mathbf{x}_{IP} is its center, eigenvectors of \mathbf{V} are the principal axes of the ellipsoid and eigenvalues are proportional to the sizes measured in the direction of the respective eigenvectors. At Belle II the shape of this ellipsoid has typical "eigen" sizes $\sigma'_y = 0.1 \mu\text{m}$, $\sigma'_x = 13 \mu\text{m}$, $\sigma'_z = 320 \mu\text{m}$.

At Belle II both \mathbf{x}_{IP} and \mathbf{V} are continuously measured using $e^+e^- \rightarrow \mu^+\mu^-$ which is a process with clean topology and high event rate. In the past, the beam spot was determined using vertices reconstructed from the two muon tracks. However, this approach highly suffers from the tracking resolution, so that an algorithm was developed which directly takes track parameters as the input. This algorithm is inspired by the approach used at BaBar [8] or CMS collaboration [11].

The general idea is that for every track in the $e^+e^- \rightarrow \mu^+\mu^-$ event holds

$$\begin{aligned} d_0^{(1)} &= x_{\text{IP}} \sin \phi_0^{(1)} - y_{\text{IP}} \cos \phi_0^{(1)} + r^{(1)}, \\ d_0^{(2)} &= x_{\text{IP}} \sin \phi_0^{(2)} - y_{\text{IP}} \cos \phi_0^{(2)} + r^{(2)}, \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where $d_0^{(1,2)}$ and $\phi_0^{(1,2)}$ are the standard track parameters for the μ^+ and μ^- defined in [5] and $x_{\text{IP}}, y_{\text{IP}}$ are the coordinates of the actual interaction point. The $r^{(1,2)}$ denotes random factors related to the tracking resolution which have spread about $15 \mu\text{m}$, but are zero on average.

When many events are considered, the equations (5) written for every event can be understood as overdetermined system of the linear equations for variables $x_{\text{IP}}, y_{\text{IP}}$. In this way, the transverse coordinates of the beam spot center are measured. Knowing the $x_{\text{IP}}, y_{\text{IP}}$, the equations (5) can be transformed to the coordinate system with origin at $(x_{\text{IP}}, y_{\text{IP}})$. Then the product of the right-hand sides of (5) can be expressed as

$$d_0'^{(1)} d_0'^{(2)} = \sigma_x^2 \sin \phi_0^{(1)} \sin \phi_0^{(2)} + \sigma_y^2 \cos \phi_0^{(1)} \cos \phi_0^{(2)} - C_{xy} \sin(\phi_0^{(1)} + \phi_0^{(2)}) + R, \quad (6)$$

where $d_0'^{(1,2)}$ are $d_0^{(1,2)}$ in the transformed system, σ_x, σ_y are the beam spot sizes and C_{xy} is the covariance which is non-zero if the beam spot is rotated. When many events are considered, the equation (6) is understood as overdetermined system of linear equations for σ_x^2, σ_y^2 and C_{xy} . Notice that terms including r cancel on average if terms like $\langle x_{\text{IP}} r^{(1)} \rangle$ or $\langle r^{(1)} r^{(2)} \rangle$ are zero when averaging over many events. This condition appears to be well satisfied, therefore most of the resolution effects are canceled in this way and the beam spot sizes can be measured with high precision. More formally, this condition means that the statistical distribution of the overall residuum R has zero mean and shape of this distribution does not depend on the phase space region which is defined by $\phi_0^{(1)}$ and $\phi_0^{(2)}$ variables.

We sketched only the general idea of the algorithm, in reality all 9 beam spot parameters are measured, i.e. also the beam spot tilts w.r.t. the z -axis, z_{IP} and σ_z . At Belle II the beam spot position is measured in ~ 30 min intervals and the remaining parameters in intervals lasting about 2 hours. Some of the measured values for data from April 2022 can be seen in Fig. 5. The xz angle of the beam spot is related to the non-zero crossing angle of the beams and to the fact that x -sizes of the beams are not equal.

3.3 Beam momenta

By design the beams do not collide head-on, but with a horizontal crossing angle of 83 mrad, where nominally both beams share half of this angle. Since the actual angles can differ from the design values, both the energies and the angles of the beams are measured, that means 3+3 parameters.

Figure 5: The time dependence of the x -coordinate of the beam spot center, horizontal beam spot size and the beam spot tilt in the xz plane. The statistical uncertainties of the x_{IP} are depicted as the light blue band, but are too small to be visible. The uncertainties of the remaining variables are not plotted as they are not stored in the Belle II Conditions Database [12].

The momenta of the beams are not measured directly, instead they are derived from the boost vector β , CM energy of the collisions E_{CMS} and the angles $\theta_{\{x,y\}z}^{\text{CMS}}$ of the collision axis in the CM system. This quantities are defined as:

$$\beta = \frac{1}{E^{\text{H}} + E^{\text{L}}}(\mathbf{p}^{\text{H}} + \mathbf{p}^{\text{L}}), \quad E_{\text{CMS}} = \sqrt{(E^{\text{H}} + E^{\text{L}})^2 - (\mathbf{p}^{\text{H}} + \mathbf{p}^{\text{L}})^2}, \quad \theta_{\{x,y\}z}^{\text{CMS}} = \text{Angle}_{\{x,y\}z}[\text{Boost}_{-\beta}(p^{\text{H}})], \quad (7)$$

where $p^{\text{H}} = (E^{\text{H}}, \mathbf{p}^{\text{H}})$ and $p^{\text{L}} = (E^{\text{L}}, \mathbf{p}^{\text{L}})$ are the 4-momenta of the colliding electron and positron, respectively. The "Boost" operator performs boost of the 4-vector and operator "Angle $_{xz}$ " returns angle of 4-vector in xz plane, i.e. $\text{atan } p_x/p_z$ for vector p , and similarly for "Angle $_{yz}$ ". The quantities β , E_{CMS} and $\theta_{\{x,y\}z}^{\text{CMS}}$ are independent and represent 6 degrees of freedom, so that they fully constrain momenta of the beams. In the following, the procedure how to measure these quantities is briefly described.

3.3.1 Boost vector

The boost vector β can be interpreted as the velocity of the CM reference frame, or the $\Upsilon(4S)$ resonance if it is produced. Similarly as the beam spot, the boost vector is also measured using $e^+e^- \rightarrow \mu^+\mu^-$ events, where it is equal to the velocity of the $\mu^+\mu^-$ system. As the angles of the tracks are measured with much better resolution than curvatures, we use an approach inspired by the procedure in [8]. For every event a direction vector perpendicular to the $\mu^+\mu^-$ plane is calculated and parametrized by its azimuthal and polar angles ϕ and λ . Consequently, for every event holds:

$$b_x \cos \phi + b_y \sin \phi = -\tan \lambda, \quad (8)$$

where $\mathbf{b} = (b_x, b_y, 1)$ is the vector pointing in the direction of the boost vector. The parameters b_x and b_y are determined from the linear regression, similarly as in case of the beam spot position (5).

The magnitude of β is measured from the average rapidity $(y'_{\mu^+} + y'_{\mu^-})/2$, where both rapidities are evaluated w.r.t. the boost direction known from the previous step. As the muons are highly relativistic, rapidity and pseudo-rapidity are almost equal, therefore, the algorithm is nearly independent on the track curvatures (momenta of the muons). The resolution of the boost vector magnitude is very good and even allows to determine the boost vector spread caused by the energy spread of the particles in the beams.

At Belle II the boost vector is measured in time intervals of ~ 8 hours and the time dependence of the measured values can be seen in Fig. 6. The nominal value of the boost vector magnitude is $|\beta| = 276.11 \times 10^{-3}$ and 150.83 mrad for boost vector angle in the xz plane. The value of the yz angle is designed to be zero.

Figure 6: The time dependence of the magnitude and xz and yz angles of the boost vector. The light blue band represents statistical uncertainties.

3.3.2 Centre-of-mass energy of the collisions

We use 2 ways to measure the CM energy of the collisions.

The first approach is based on the hadronic B decays $B \rightarrow D^{(*)}\pi$, where both charged and neutral B mesons are considered. As the B mesons are nearly at rest in the CM system, the momentum of the B in the CMS, p_B^* , is highly sensitive to the E_{CMS} . The CM energy is then obtained from the fit to the $E_B^* = \sqrt{m_B^2 + (p_B^*)^2}$ which is peaking at $E_{\text{CMS}}/2$. Good E_B^* resolution even allows to measure the E_{CMS} spread, similarly as for the boost vector magnitude. The disadvantage of this method is low rate of the events and bias from the E_{CMS} dependence of the $e^+e^- \rightarrow \Upsilon(4S)$ resonance cross section which has to be taken into account.

Alternatively, we also measure E_{CMS} using invariant mass of the $\mu\mu$ system in $e^+e^- \rightarrow \mu^+\mu^-$ events, where the event rate is much higher. Unfortunately, the tracking resolution effects lead to a peak width of ~ 40 MeV which is much more than the E_{CMS} spread of ~ 5 MeV stemming from the energy spread of the beams. Also the systematic uncertainty of the muon momentum scale can affect the peak position by several MeV whereas for the first method the momentum scale uncertainty is much lower as the B meson decay products have much smaller momenta. The $\mu\mu$ method is still useful to track short time variations of E_{CMS} while the overall normalization and the E_{CMS} spread are fixed from the hadronic B decays. We also use $\mu\mu$ method for special runs not targeting $\Upsilon(4S)$ resonance, i.e. for runs with energy below $B\bar{B}$ production threshold or for runs at higher energies, up to 10810 MeV.

The historical time dependence of the E_{CMS} measured at Belle II is shown in Fig. 7. It can be seen,

Figure 7: The time dependence of the centre-of-mass energy of the collisions as measured by the Belle II. The nominal energy corresponding to the $\Upsilon(4S)$ mass is depicted as a green line. Only runs with nominal energy corresponding to $\Upsilon(4S)$ resonance are plotted.

that for a significant time period the detector operated slightly below the resonance. That was corrected in 2021-11-25, when SuperKEKB performed new energy scan to adjust the beam energies. From that time the energy slightly decreased again. Larger deviations from the nominal energy lead to lower $B\bar{B}$ event rate and should be avoided.

3.3.3 Collisions axis in the CMS and the beam momenta

The boost vector β allows to transform to the CMS. In this system, obtained by the Lorentz boost, the colliding particles have momenta of equal size and opposite orientation. However, in general, the collision axis is not aligned with the z' axis of the system. Therefore, to transform to the classical CMS, where particles collide in the z' direction, an extra rotation has to be performed by angles $\theta_{\{x,y\}z}^{\text{CMS}}$ defined in (7).

Experimentally, these angles can be measured in $e^+e^- \rightarrow \mu^+\mu^-e^+e^-$ events, where invariant mass of the $\mu^+\mu^-$ pair is required to be below 2 GeV. The flight direction of the $\mu^+\mu^-$ pair measured in the CMS obtained by the Lorentz boost directly corresponds to the $\theta_{\{x,y\}z}^{\text{CMS}}$ angles. This process has a high event rate, so the time intervals of ~ 8 hours can be utilized. Measured values of θ_{xz}^{CMS} and θ_{yz}^{CMS} are typically about 5.3 mrad and -0.2 mrad and slightly differ from the nominal values 5.8 mrad and 0 mrad.

From β , E_{CMS} and $\theta_{\{x,y\}z}^{\text{CMS}}$ the beam momentum vectors can be derived by inverting (7), see Fig. 8. These

Figure 8: The time dependence of the electron (HER) and positron (LER) beam angles in the xz and yz plane. In addition, the positron beam energy is plotted on the right plot.

momenta are important, for example, for the run-dependent Monte Carlo production, where they are used as an input. Since β and $\theta_{\{x,y\}z}^{\text{CMS}}$ differ from the nominal values also the measured angles slightly differ from the designed values which are 41.5 mrad in the xz plane and 0 mrad in the yz plane. There are differences also the beam energies, especially energy of the positron beam is slightly lower w.r.t. the nominal one as shown in Fig. 8.

It is worth to mention that the beam momentum vectors form a plane and this plane by design should coincide with $x'z'$ plane of the beam spot, otherwise the crossing of the beams is not optimal and there is a luminosity loss. From our preliminary studies we see a consistence between these two planes within statistical uncertainties.

4 Conclusions

The Belle II tracking shows excellent performance and with increasing integrated luminosity there are more and more physics results, including the world-leading measurements of the lifetimes of the charmed hadrons. The tracking software is being continuously developed, one of the latest improvements is the implementation SVDHough algorithm for the standalone track finding in SVD which is planned to replace VXDTF2 algorithm. To fully benefit from the clear topology of the e^+e^- collisions, the beam-related variables must

be continuously monitored. Quantities like beam spot, boost vector and CM collision energy are used for the data analysis, for the Monte Carlo production as well as for monitoring of the accelerator performance.

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